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Evaluation of Bayesian Multimodel Estimation in Surface Incident Shortwave Radiation Simulation over High Latitude Areas

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Abstract: Surface incident shortwave radiation (SSR) is crucial for understanding the Earth's climate change issues. Simulations from general circulation models (GCMs) are one of the most practical ways to produce long-term global SSR products. Although previous studies have comprehensively assessed the performance of the GCMs in simulating SSR globally or regionally, studies assessing the performance of these models over high-latitude areas are sparse. This study evaluated and intercompared the SSR simulations of 48 GCMs participating in the fifth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) using quality-controlled SSR surface measurements at 44 radiation sites from three observation networks (GC-NET, BSRN, and GEBA) and the SSR retrievals from the Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System, Energy Balanced and Filled (CERES EBAF) data set over high-latitude areas from 2000 to 2005. Furthermore, this study evaluated the performance of the SSR estimations of two multimodel ensemble methods, i.e., the simple model averaging (SMA) and the Bayesian model averaging (BMA) methods. The seasonal performance of the SSR estimations of individual GCMs, the SMA method, and the BMA method were also intercompared. The evaluation results indicated that there were large deficiencies in the performance of the individual GCMs in simulating SSR, and these GCM SSR simulations did not show a tendency to overestimate the SSR over high-latitude areas. Moreover, the ensemble SSR estimations generated by the SMA and BMA methods were superior to all individual GCM SSR simulations over high-latitude areas, and the estimations of the BMA method were the best compared to individual GCM simulations and the SMA method-based estimations. Compared to the CERES EBAF SSR retrievals, the uncertainties of the SSR estimations of the GCMs, the SMA method, and the BMA method are relatively large during summer.

Keywords: Bayesian model averaging; surface incident shortwave radiation; CMIP5; general circulation models; multimodel ensembles; high-latitude areas

1. Introduction

Surface incident shortwave radiation (SSR) is not only an important parameter in many atmospheric, oceanic, and land process models [1], but also a critical ingredient in energy exchanges between the Earth's surface and the atmosphere [2]. It also plays an important role in the hydrological and carbon cycles [3–5] and ultimately influences the Earth's climate. Therefore, knowing the spatial distribution and temporal evolution of SSR is essential for improving our understanding of the Earth's climate and climate change.

SSR is usually obtained through four methods: surface measurements, satellite retrievals, reanalysis products, and general circulation models (GCMs) simulations [6]. GCMs have become an important tool for producing spatially and temporally continuous long-term global products of energy balance components. Many studies have investigated the performance of *SSR* simulations from the GCMs at both global and regional scales [7–11]. For instance, Ma et al. [9] found that the biases of the global average *SSR* simulations varied from 4.8 W m^{-2} to 11.9 W m^{-2} among the 48 fifth phase of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) models compared to the ground observations from 446 stations during 2000–2005. In addition, the CMIP5-simulated multimodel mean *SSR* using the simple model averaging (SMA) method had a bias value of 2.6 W m^{-2} compared with the *SSR* retrievals from the Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System, Energy Balanced And Filled (CERES EBAF) over the globe, 4.7 W m^{-2} and 1.7 W m^{-2} over land and oceans, respectively. Wild et al. [10] evaluated 43 CMIP5 models with *SSR* observations at ground sites during 2000–2004 from the Global Energy Balance Archive (GEBA) and Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) networks. The root mean squared errors (RMSEs) of the annual average *SSR* ranged from 18.3 W m^{-2} to 35.2 W m^{-2} among the GCMs with respect to the 760 GEBA sites. These studies indicated that large uncertainties in the simulated *SSR* exist among the GCMs, and GCMs exhibit systematic bias, i.e., the simulated *SSR* values are usually greater than the observed values. It was also found that the differences in physical basis, parameterization schemes, and coupling schemes were the major reason for various uncertainties in climate change [12].

Although previous studies have comprehensively assessed the performance of GCMs in simulating *SSR* globally or regionally, studies assessing the performance of these GCMs over high-latitude areas are sparse. Compared with low-latitude regions, high-latitude areas are most vulnerable to global warming and thus experience more dramatic environmental changes [13]. The dramatic changes of environment in high-latitude areas may cause changes in cloud and surface albedo, and may further disturb the surface radiation budget [14]. In addition, the remote sensing surface radiation retrieval methods are also very problematic in high-latitude areas [15], likely because it is hard to distinguish between the snow/ice and cloud, which widely cover high-latitude areas and are hard to be accurately estimated under the cloud retrieval schemes [13,16].

Different GCMs have their own strengths and weaknesses when simulating the *SSR* [17]. The multimodel ensemble (MME) methods are able to postprocess the GCM simulations with equal or unequal weights. It is found that a SMA method is able to perform better than any individual GCM in estimating climatic and energy budget variables [12,18–20]. In addition to the traditional SMA method, more sophisticated MME methods are proposed wherein the participating single models are given different weights [19–23]. In general, the sophisticated MME methods perform better than the SMA method [19–21,24,25].

Among the sophisticated MME methods, the Bayesian model averaging (BMA) method is one of the most promising methods [12]. Based on Bayesian inference, the statistical postprocessing method can not only provide an expectation but also a probability density function (PDF) of any quantity of interest based on the training data [12]. This advantage makes the BMA method a widely used postprocessing method in various essential climate variable estimations and predictions, such as global surface air temperature predictions [20] and hydrological predictions [26]. Studies have found that the BMA method produces more accurate and reliable outputs than the individual GCMs and other MME methods [19,24,25]. However, the BMA method is still rarely used in *SSR* estimation.

This study evaluated the *SSR* simulations from 48 CMIP5 models using the quality-controlled surface observations between 2000 and 2005 from 21 Greenland Climate Network (GC-NET) sites, 5 BSRN sites, and 18 GEBA sites in the high-latitude areas ($>60^\circ$) and compared these *SSR* simulations with the *SSR* satellite retrievals from CERES EBAF, which have the most accurate *SSR* retrievals among satellite-based products [6]. We evaluated the *SSR* simulations and intercompared the performance of both the SMA and BMA methods for estimating the *SSR* in high-latitude areas. The seasonal performance of the outputs from individual GCMs, the SMA method, and the BMA method were also intercompared.

This paper is organized as follows. The *SSR* data used in this study are described in Section 2. The methodology for the evaluation is given in Section 3. The results are analyzed in Section 4, and the study is concluded and discussed in Section 5.

2. Data

Three kinds of *SSR* data are used in this study: CMIP5 simulations, ground measurements, and satellite retrievals. The details of these data sets are described in the following subsections.

2.1. CMIP5 GCMs

The CMIP5 in the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC AR5) provides simulations from a number of GCMs developed and maintained by different institutions around the world [17]. These data have been organized by the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison (PCMDI) for the IPCC AR5. Compared to the third phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP3) in the fourth IPCC assessment report (IPCC AR4), the GCMs in IPCC AR5 have many improved model types, with more interactive components, including aerosols, dynamic vegetation, atmospheric physics and carbon and hydrological cycles [24]. Most dynamic, physical, and chemical algorithms were also improved in the IPCC AR5 models [10,11].

At the time of this study, 48 GCM simulations of *SSR* were available. We selected the "r1i1p1" ensemble and the "historical" experiment, which was aimed at accurately reconstructing the climate evolution of the 20th century by considering all major natural and anthropogenic forcing factors, such as changes in atmospheric greenhouse gases, aerosol loadings (tropospheric and stratospheric volcanic), solar output, and land use [11]. Most historical and r1i1p1 simulations in CMIP5 were run for the period from 1850 to 2005.

The spatial resolution of the 48 CMIP5 GCMs used in this study varies from $0.56^\circ \times 0.56^\circ$ to $3.75^\circ \times 3.75^\circ$. Detailed information on the 48 CMIP5 GCMs, host institutions, countries, and spatial resolutions, is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Detailed information of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) general circulation models (GCMs) used in this study.

ID	Model Name	Institute ID	Country	Resolution
1	ACCESS1.0	CSIRO-BOM	Australia	1.88° × 1.24°
2	ACCESS1.3	CSIRO-BOM	Australia	1.88° × 1.24°
3	BCC-CSM1.1(m)	BCC	China	1.13° × 1.13°
4	BCC-CSM1.1	BCC	China	2.81° × 2.81°
5	BNU-ESM	GCESS	China	2.81° × 2.81°
6	CanCM4	CCCMA	Canada	2.81° × 2.81°
7	CanESM2	CCCMA	Canada	2.81° × 2.81°
8	CCSM4	NCAR	USA	1.25° × 0.94°
9	CESM1-BGC	NSF-DOE-NCAR	USA	1.25° × 0.94°
10	CESM1-CAM5	NSF-DOE-NCAR	USA	1.25° × 0.94°
11	CESM1-CAM5.1.FV2	NSF-DOE-NCAR	USA	2.50° × 1.88°
12	CESM1-FASTCHEM	NSF-DOE-NCAR	USA	1.25° × 0.94°
13	CESM1-WACCM	NSF-DOE-NCAR	USA	2.50° × 1.88°
14	CMCC-CESM	CMCC	Italy	3.75° × 3.75°
15	CMCC-CMS	CMCC	Italy	1.88° × 1.88°
16	CMCC-CM	CMCC	Italy	0.75° × 0.75°
17	CNRM-CM5.2	CNRM-CERFACS	France	1.41° × 1.41°
18	CNRM-CM5	CNRM-CERFACS	France	1.41° × 1.41°
19	CSIRO-Mk3.6.0	CSIRO-QCCCE	Australia	1.88° × 1.88°
20	FGOALS-g2	LASG-CESS	China	2.81° × 3.00°
21	FIO-ESM	FIO	China	2.81° × 2.81°
22	GFDL-CM2p1	NOAA GFDL	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
23	GFDL-CM3	NOAA GFDL	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
24	GFDL-ESM2G	NOAA GFDL	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
25	GFDL-ESM2M	NOAA GFDL	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
26	GISS-E2-H-CC	NOAA GISS	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
27	GISS-E2-H	NOAA GISS	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
28	GISS-E2-R-CC	NOAA GISS	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
29	GISS-E2-R	NOAA GISS	USA	2.50° × 2.00°
30	HadCM3	MOHC	UK	3.75° × 3.47°
31	HadGEM2-AO	NIMR/KMA	Korea/UK	1.88° × 1.24°
32	HadGEM2-CC	MOHC	UK	1.88° × 1.24°
33	HadGEM2-ES	MOHC	UK	1.88° × 1.24°
34	INM-CM4	UNM	Russia	2.00° × 1.50°
35	IPSL-CM5A-LR	IPSL	France	3.75° × 1.88°
36	IPSL-CM5A-MR	IPSL	France	2.50° × 1.26°
37	IPSL-CM5B-LR	IPSL	France	3.75° × 1.88°
38	MIROC-ESM-CHEM	MIROC	Japan	2.81° × 2.81°
39	MIROC-ESM	MIROC	Japan	2.81° × 2.81°
40	MIROC4h	MIROC	Japan	0.56° × 0.56°
41	MIROC5	MIROC	Japan	1.41° × 1.41°
42	MPI-ESM-LR	MPI-M	Germany	1.88° × 1.88°
43	MPI-ESM-MR	MPI-M	Germany	1.88° × 1.88°
44	MPI-ESM-P	MPI-M	Germany	1.88° × 1.88°
45	MPI-CGCM3	MRI	Japan	1.13° × 1.13°
46	MPI-ESM1	NCC	Norway	1.13° × 1.13°
47	NorESM1-ME	NCC	Norway	2.50° × 1.88°
48	NorESM1-M	NCC	Norway	2.50° × 1.88°

2.2. Ground Measurements

Ground observations of *SSR* over high-latitude areas used to evaluate *SSR* estimates stem from three networks: BSRN (five sites) [27], GC-NET (21 sites) [28], and GEBA (18 sites) [29]. Figure 1 shows the geographical distributions of the observation sites used in this study.

Figure 1. Geographical distributions of the observation sites (44 sites in total) used in this study from Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) (5 sites in blue dots), Greenland Climate Network (GC-NET) (21 sites in green triangles), and Global Energy Balance Archive (GEBA) (18 sites in pink asterisks).

The BSRN was operational in the early 1990s and was established by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) to provide radiation measurements of high accuracy and high temporal resolution at a limited number of sites in various climate zones [30]. The *SSR* measurement instruments at BSRN sites are calibrated every six months and regularly maintain a *SSR* uncertainty of less than 5% [27]. To improve data continuity, the *SSR* was measured by two parallel observation systems [27]. At present, the BSRN project has archived more than 60 sites covering a wide latitude range from 89.98° S to 82.49° N and a wide longitude range from 156.61° W to 169.69° E [2].

The GC-NET consists of more than 20 automatic weather stations (AWSs) mainly distributed in the accumulation areas of ice sheets. GC-NET AWSs are equipped with various factory-calibrated instruments to measure surface energy and mass balance components [31]. By 2013, all the AWS have gone through a rigorous data quality control process to reduce interference from the typical problems experienced by unattended weather stations, such as station tilt, low cosine responses at large solar zenith angles, riming on sensor domes, and sensor overheating [32]. The GC-NET provides hourly radiation observations with instruments located between 0.1 and 5 m above the surface, depending on the local accumulation rates and tower heights.

The GEBA is a database maintained at ETH Zurich (Switzerland) for the central storage of worldwide measured energy fluxes at the Earth's surface [33,34]. The current version (2017) contains 2500 worldwide locations with an average of approximately 500,000 monthly entries of various surface energy balance components [33]. Thus, the *SSR* is the most widely measured quantity in the GEBA. The GEBA has undergone substantial changes in terms of available data, data access, and internet appearance and has been widely used to evaluate the *SSR* estimates from satellite observations, reanalysis data, and GCMs [6].

Since the BSRN and the GC-NET only provide instantaneous values of the *SSR*, critical quality control procedures were applied to estimate the monthly *SSR* observations from the instantaneous values of the surface measurements from the GC-NET and the BSRN. First, the daily mean *SSR* were obtained by integrating the instantaneous values in a day which has at least 80 percent valid observed values. The missing data were estimated via the simple linear interpolation method. Then, the monthly values were calculated by averaging the available daily values within the month. If daily mean *SSR* data were missing for more than 10 days in one month, the monthly *SSR* data were excluded from the evaluation.

The CERES EBAF *SSR* products begin in 2000, and most CMIP5 GCMs *SSR* simulations end in 2005. Therefore, the study period is the overlap: 2000–2005. A subset of the 21 GC-NET sites, five BSRN sites, and 18 GEBA sites at high-latitude areas, which provides at least 10 months of records within

the period of 2000–2005, was used in this study. Detailed information of the sites used in this study, including their latitudes, longitudes, and elevations, is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Detailed information of the sites from GC-NET, BSRN, and GEBA used in this study.

Network	Site Name	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Elevation (m)
GC-NET	Swiss Camp	69.57 N	49.32 W	1149
GC-NET	Crawford Pt.	69.88 N	46.99 W	2022
GC-NET	NASA-U	73.84 N	49.50 W	2369
GC-NET	GITS	77.14 N	61.04 W	1887
GC-NET	Humboldt	78.53 N	56.83 W	1995
GC-NET	Summit	72.58 N	38.51 W	3254
GC-NET	TUNU-N	78.02 N	33.99 W	2113
GC-NET	DYE-2	66.48 N	46.28 W	2165
GC-NET	JAR	69.50 N	49.68 W	962
GC-NET	Saddle	66.00 N	44.50 W	2559
GC-NET	South Dome	63.15 N	44.82 W	2922
GC-NET	NASA-E	75.00 N	30.00 W	2631
GC-NET	CP2	69.88 N	46.99 W	1990
GC-NET	NGRIP	75.31 N	42.33 W	2950
GC-NET	NASA-SE	66.48 N	42.50 W	2425
GC-NET	KAR	69.70 N	33.00 W	2579
GC-NET	JAR2	69.42 N	50.06 W	568
GC-NET	JAR3	69.39 N	50.31 W	283
GC-NET	Aurora	67.15 N	47.29 W	1798
GC-NET	Petermann Gl.	80.68 N	60.23 W	37
GC-NET	PeterMann ELA	80.09 N	58.07 W	965
BSRN	Barrow	71.32 N	156.61 E	8
BSRN	Georg von Neumayer	70.65 S	8.25 W	42
BSRN	Ny-Ålesund	78.93 N	11.93 E	11
BSRN	South Pole	89.98 S	24.80 W	2800
BSRN	Syowa	69.01 S	39.59 E	18
GEBA	Oimyakon	63.27 N	143.15 E	726
GEBA	Vanavara	60.33 N	102.26 E	259
GEBA	Verkhoyansk	67.55 N	133.38 E	137
GEBA	Yakutsk	62.08 N	129.75 E	103
GEBA	Bergen	60.40 N	5.32 E	45
GEBA	Borlaenge	60.43 N	15.50 E	153
GEBA	Helsinki-Airport	60.32 N	24.97 E	53
GEBA	Jokioinen	60.82 N	23.50 E	104
GEBA	Jyvaskyla-Airpt.	62.40 N	25.68 E	141
GEBA	Kiruna	67.85 N	20.23 E	505
GEBA	Lerwick	60.13 N	1.18 W	82
GEBA	Lulea	65.55 N	22.13 E	16
GEBA	Oestersund	63.18 N	14.50 E	876
GEBA	Reykjavik	64.13 N	21.90 W	52
GEBA	Sodankyla	67.37 N	26.65 E	178
GEBA	Umea	63.82 N	20.25 E	10
GEBA	Utsjoki, Kevo	69.75 N	27.03 E	107
GEBA	Resolute	74.72 N	94.98 W	67

2.3. CERES EBAF SSR Retrievals

The distribution of the radiation ground sites is widespread as shown in Figure 1, but gaps remain particularly over the Antarctic continent and the high-latitude oceans. Thus, this study also evaluated the SSR estimations from the MME methods and individual GCMs by comparing them with the satellite SSR retrievals, which can provide globally gridded values of the SSR. The monthly mean satellite derived SSR retrievals with a spatial resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ from the CERES EBAF product (Ed 4.0),

which has been reported to be more accurate than other gridded SSR products [2,9,35], are used in this study.

The CERES EBAF retrieves shortwave fluxes based on TOA radiance observations from the passive Terra, Aqua, and Suomi-National Polar-Orbiting Partnership satellites [36]. Moreover, the surface irradiances are adjusted using radiative kernels in the retrieval algorithm of the CERES EBAF. The surface irradiance adjustment process is composed of bias correction and a Lagrange multiplier [37]. In the bias correction process, the bias in the temperature and the specific humidity between 200 and 500 h Pa is corrected based on observations incorporated from the atmospheric infrared sounder (AIRS), which is on board the MODIS-Aqua satellite. The bias in the cloud fraction (CF) is corrected based on the observations from the Cloud–Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations (CALIPSO) and CloudSat. In the Lagrange multiplier process, errors in the surface, cloud, and atmospheric properties are corrected. Over the high-latitude areas, the cloud properties are derived from the Terra and Aqua reflectance data using one of two retrieval algorithms depending on the existence of snow and ice [36,38]. To reduce the error in the surface irradiances and to increase the consistency in the TOA irradiances, surface irradiances are constrained using the CERES-derived TOA irradiance [39].

3. Methods

3.1. Bayesian Model Averaging (BMA) Method

The BMA method provides a way to combine different models to a multimodel and is a promising method for calibrating ensembles in forecasts [40]. Standard statistical analysis (e.g., regression analysis), proceeds conditionally on one assumed statistical model, which may be selected from among several possible competing models. Other models can also provide different results but with different uncertainties. BMA [41,42] overcomes the problem by conditioning, not on a single/best model, but on the entire ensemble of statistical models considered. To better take advantage of the GCM simulations and obtain more reliable results, we used the BMA method to combine 48 GCM SSR simulations.

In the BMA method, the output is a PDF, which is a weighted average of the conditional PDFs, weighted by their posterior model probabilities. We denote the quantity to be forecasted by y . The law of total probability gives the combined forecast PDF of the quantity y by:

$$p(y|y^T) = \sum_{i=1}^K p(y|X_i, y^T)p(X_i|y^T) \quad (1)$$

where $p(y|X_i, y^T)$ is the forecast PDF based on model X_i alone, estimated from the training data y^T , and K is the number of models using to be combined. $p(X_i|y^T)$ denotes the posterior probability of model X_i is the best given the training data, reflecting how well model X_i matches the training data. According to the Bayesian theory, this term is computed by:

$$p(X_i|y^T) = \frac{p(y^T|X_i)p(X_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^K p(y^T|X_j)p(X_j)} \quad (2)$$

The initial value of $p(X_i)$ can be assigned based on the previous knowledge of the model performance. In this study, uniform prior is assigned $p(X_i) = \frac{1}{K}$. Thus, Equation (2) can be further simplified and rewritten as:

$$p(X_i|y^T) = \frac{p(y^T|X_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^K p(y^T|X_j)} \quad (3)$$

Because BMA method assumes that the model forecasts are unbiased, the bias-correction methods should be applied in advance. The linear regression method is applied for each GCM SSR simulations:

$$f_i = a_i + b_i \cdot y_i \quad (4)$$

where f_i denotes the bias-corrected forecast for model X_i and y_i is the forecast of the variable from model X_i . Unique coefficients a_i and b_i for each model X_i are determined through least squares approximation, with the observations in the training period as the dependent variable and the forecasts as the explanatory variables.

Considering the application of BMA method to bias-corrected forecast f_i , Equation (1) can be rewritten as:

$$p(y|f_1, \dots, f_K, y^T) = \sum_{i=1}^K w_i p_i(y|f_i, y^T) \quad (5)$$

where $w_i = p(X_i|y^T)$ is the BMA weight for model X_i computed from the training data and reflects the relative performance of model X_i on the training period. The BMA weights are nonnegative and add up to 1. The conditional probabilities $p_i(y|f_i, y^T)$ can be interpreted as the conditional PDF of y conditional on f_i and training data y^T . These conditional PDFs are assumed to be normally distributed for computational convenience as:

$$y|(f_i, y^T) \sim N(a_i + b_i y_i, \sigma^2) \quad (6)$$

where the coefficients a_i and b_i are calculated from the bias-correction procedure described above. This means that the BMA predictive distribution becomes a weighted sum of normal distributions, with equal variance and centered at the bias-corrected forecast. A deterministic forecast can be obtained using the conditional expectation of y given the forecasts:

$$E[y|(f_1, \dots, f_K, y^T)] = \sum_{i=1}^K w_i (a_i + b_i f_i) \quad (7)$$

The BMA weights and the variance are estimated by the maximum likelihood [43] from the training dataset. For given parameters to be estimated, the likelihood function is defined as the probability of the training data and is viewed as a function of the parameters. The BMA weights and variance are used to maximize this function, that is, the parameter values for which the observations were most likely to have been observed. It is convenient to maximize the log-likelihood function rather than the likelihood function itself. Following the recommendation of Raftery et al. [44], we use the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [45] to maximize the log-likelihood function. In brief, the EM algorithm is iterative and alternates between the E (or expectation) step and the M (or maximization) step. More detailed description of the BMA method is provided by Raftery et al. [44].

In this study, the SSR ground observations over six years (2000–2005) from 44 stations spread across high-latitude areas were randomly selected as the training (22 stations) and testing (22 stations) data for the BMA analysis.

3.2. Statistical Measures

3.2.1. Normalized RMSE

To evaluate the performance of the SSR estimations from individual GCMs and the MME methods, the bias between simulations and reference data, the corresponding RMSE and correlation coefficient (R) were calculated. These three statistics can quantify the similarity between the simulations and the reference data.

To compare the RMSE of each GCM SSR simulation more intuitively, the average RMSEs were normalized following [46]. The normalization results are called nRMSEs, which are defined as follows:

$$nRMSE = \frac{RMSE - RMSE_m}{RMSE_m} \quad (8)$$

where $RMSE_m$, the “typical” GCM error, is defined as the median of RMSE values. We use the median rather than the average value here to prevent GCMs with unusually large errors (outliers) from unduly affecting the results. The nRMSE is a measure of how well a GCM (with respect to particular surface observations) compares with the typical GCM error. If $nRMSE > 0$, then the GCM is inferior to the typical GCM (the GCM whose RMSE is determined as $RMSE_m$); the greater the nRMSE value is, the worse the GCM. Conversely, if $nRMSE < 0$, then the GCM is better than the typical GCM; the smaller the nRMSE value (greater than -1), the better the GCM.

3.2.2. Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency

The performance of the SSR estimations from the GCMs, the SMA method, and the BMA method was also evaluated by the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE), which reflects how close the plot of the model simulation versus observed data is to the 1:1 line. The NSE is calculated as follows:

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - M_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (9)$$

where O_i and M_i are the observed and estimated SSR, respectively. n is the size of data. \bar{O} is the average value of the observed SSR. The NSE can range from $-\infty$ to 1, with higher values indicating better agreement.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1. Evaluating CMIP5 GCMs SSR Simulations with Ground Measurements

The simulated SSR values on the original grid scale were directly compared with the ground SSR observations within the grid cells. Before evaluation, all the GCM SSR simulations were re-projected into a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution using bilinear interpolation since they have different spatial resolutions. This study chose 44 sites from three networks with more than ten months of available SSR data between 2000 and 2005. Four statistical parameters were used to evaluate the individual GCM: R, RMSE, bias, and nRMSE. All the calculations were performed based on the monthly averages of the six year (2000–2005) time series.

The calculation results of the bias, RMSE and R for the 48 GCM SSR simulations were labeled on the scatter plots (Figure 2), and the bias, RMSE, and R histograms for the 48 GCM SSR simulations are shown in Figure 3. The biases in the GCM SSR simulations compared with the ground observations for all sites vary from -30 W m^{-2} to 15 W m^{-2} and only slightly more than half (only 26 GCMs) of the GCMs overestimate the SSR. Overall, the GCMs do not show an obvious tendency to overestimate the SSR over high-latitude areas. The absolute bias values of 28 GCM simulations are within 5 W m^{-2} . The biases of 11 GCMs SSR simulations range from 5 to 15 W m^{-2} . The biases of 9 GCM SSR simulations are less than -5 W m^{-2} . The MIROC4h SSR simulations have the largest positive bias of 13.23 W m^{-2} , followed by the GISS-E2-R-CC and GISS-E2-R SSR simulations, which have approximately the same bias values. Among the GCMs that underestimate the SSR when compared to the ground observations, the CMCC-CESM SSR simulations have the largest negative bias of approximately -28.98 W m^{-2} , the largest RMSE and the smallest R. The underestimation of SSR over high-latitude areas may be due to an overestimation of the total cloud cover in this region [9,47].

Figure 2. Scatterplots of the monthly surface incident shortwave radiation (SSR) observations from 44 sites (red dots: surface observations from BSRN sites, black dots: surface observations from GC-NET sites, blue dots: surface observations from GEBA) and individual general circulation models (GCMs) simulations from 2000 to 2005 (in units of $W m^{-2}$).

Figure 2 also illustrates that most GCM SSR simulations result in an RMSE in the range of 20–50 $W m^{-2}$ and a large R above 0.90. Figure 3b,c illustrates that most of the GCM (36 GCMs) SSR simulations have RMSEs between 25 and 30 $W m^{-2}$ and R above 0.965, respectively. Among the 48 GCMs, the CMCC-CESM SSR simulations yield the maximum RMSE of 48.75 $W m^{-2}$, followed by the FGOALS-g2 SSR simulations with a RMSE of 38.86 $W m^{-2}$. The GFDL-CM3 SSR simulations has the smallest RMSE of 23.74 $W m^{-2}$, followed by the ACCESS 1.3 SSR simulations with a RMSE of

24.18 $W m^{-2}$. GCMs with higher spatial resolutions did not always have a lower RMSE than those with lower spatial resolutions (such as FGOALS-g2).

Figure 3. Bias (a), root mean squared errors (RMSE) (a) and R (c) histograms for monthly SSR simulations from 48 GCMs.

To further assess the influence of the radiation ground site selections and the quality of the measurements on the evaluation of the SSR simulations over high-latitude areas, this study repeated the above analysis with the sites from GEBA, BSRN, and GC-NET, respectively. The RMSEs at the BSRN sites for the individual GCM SSR simulations range from 15 to 40 $W m^{-2}$. These RMSEs are typically smaller than those from the GEBA and the GC-Net sites. However, the absolute bias values averaged over the five BSRN sites for most GCM SSR simulations are not smaller than the absolute average bias values from the 18 GEBA and 21 GC-NET sites. The SSR is underestimated by the 48 GCMs for the BSRN sites by 1.23 $W m^{-2}$, which is close to the average bias for the GC-NET sites ($-0.97 W m^{-2}$), while the average bias for the GEBA sites is 1.62 $W m^{-2}$. The R at the BSRN sites for the individual GCM SSR simulations are typically larger than those at the GEBA and the GC-Net sites. Meanwhile, the R averaged over the 18 GEBA sites for most GCMs SSR simulations are typically smaller than the average R for the five BSRN and 21 GC-NET sites.

To compare the RMSEs of each GCM SSR simulation more intuitively, the $RMSE_m$ and the nRMSEs were also calculated. In this analysis, the $RMSE_m$ was approximately 27.88 $W m^{-2}$. As shown in Figure 4, the GCMs SSR simulations with negative nRMSEs are all greater than -0.2 , which illustrates that their RMSE are only slightly smaller than the $RMSE_m$. The RMSE of the GCM SSR simulations with positive nRMSEs are obviously larger than $RMSE_m$. Among the GCM SSR simulations with negative nRMSEs, the GFDL-CM3 SSR simulations have the smallest nRMSE of -0.15 , followed by the ACCESS1.3 (-0.13) and GFDL-ESM2M (-0.10) SSR simulations. Among the GCMs with positive nRMSEs, the CMCC-CESM SSR simulations have the largest nRMSE of 0.71, followed by the FGOALS-g2 (0.39) and BNU-ESM (0.28) SSR simulations.

Figure 4. Normalized root mean squared errors (nRMSEs) of monthly SSR estimated from GCMs from 2000 to 2005.

4.2. Evaluating the MME Method Results with the Ground Measurements and the CERES EBAF Retrievals

This study used the SMA and BMA methods to generate higher accuracy SSR estimations by combining 48 GCMs SSR simulations. Figure 5 shows the weights of the individual GCMs calculated by the BMA method. The weights vary across GCMs. The greatest contributor to the SSR ensemble is the GFDL-ESM2G which has the largest weight (0.0272), more than 30% larger than the priori weight (0.0208), followed by GFDL-ESM2M (0.0259), CESM1-CAM5.1.FV2 (0.0254), and HadCM3 (0.0250). The weight of FGOALS-g2 is only 0.0123, which is about 40% lower than the priori weight, because of its relatively poor performance.

Figure 5. Relative weights of 48 GCMs calculated by the Bayesian model averaging (BMA) method.

Based on Figure 6, obvious and expected improvements in R occur for the results of the BMA method; specifically, the bias is 0.10 W m^{-2} and the RMSE is 16.79 W m^{-2} , which are lower than those of the SMA method. Although Figure 6 shows that the estimations from the BMA and SMA methods have clear advantages over the CERES EBAF retrievals in reducing the biases, the estimations of the two methods neither reduce the RMSE nor increase the R compared with the CERES EBAF retrievals.

Figure 6. Evaluation of monthly SSR estimated from the Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System, Energy Balanced and Filled (CERES EBAF), simple model averaging (SMA) method, and BMA method from 2000 to 2005 (in units of W m^{-2}).

The SSR estimations from the SMA and BMA methods were also compared with the CERES EBAF SSR retrievals over high-latitude areas as shown in Figure 7. Bilinear interpolations are applied, to make the spatial resolution of these gridded GCM SSR simulations with different spatial resolutions consistent with that of the CERES EBAF SSR retrievals with a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution.

Figure 7. Geographical distribution of the different values (a) between the BMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals, (b) between the SMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals, and (c) between the SMA results and the BMA results from 2000 to 2005 (in units of $W m^{-2}$). The results shown in (c) is 1–2 orders of magnitude smaller than those in (a) and (b).

Figure 7a,b shows the geographical distribution of the differences between the BMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals and between the SMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000

to 2005, respectively. There are obvious geographical patterns in the differences over high-latitude areas, which may be attributed to the uncertainties in the representation of the cloud microphysical processes in the GCMs. From Figure 7a, the BMA estimations commonly show positive biases over inland Antarctica, the seas around Antarctica, and the seas of the Arctic Ocean (the Greenland Sea, the Labrador Sea, and the Barents Sea). However, negative biases are found in many other regions, particularly in the high-latitude areas of Eurasia and North America, the central part of the Arctic Ocean, much of Greenland, and the coast of Antarctica. The largest negative bias is found in Iceland, up to -36.67 W m^{-2} , and the largest positive bias is found in eastern seas near Antarctica, up to 26.70 W m^{-2} .

To directly compare the geographical distribution of the SMA results and the BMA results, we calculate the different SSR values between the SMA results and the BMA results (Figure 7c). The geographical differences between the BMA results and the SMA results are much more distinct than the statistical calculation results (Figure 6). From Figure 7c, relative to the SMA results, the BMA results yield lower SSR over almost all the high-latitude areas, except Greenland and coastal areas of Antarctica. Grids with large SSR differences are concentrated in the coastal regions of Antarctica and Greenland, Europe, and Iceland and the seas around them. This geographical dissimilarity is mainly attributed to the differences weights assigned by the BMA method to different GCM SSR simulations, and the BMA results are more accurate than the SMA results.

Figures 8 and 9 show the seasonal geographical distributions of the differences between the BMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals and between the SMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals over high-latitude areas, respectively. It is obvious that the differences are typically larger over high-latitude areas during local spring (MAM in the Northern Hemisphere and SON in the Southern Hemisphere) when the sea ice begins to melt in summer (JJA in the Northern Hemisphere and DJF in the Southern Hemisphere). During local fall (SON in the Northern Hemisphere and MAM in the Southern Hemisphere) and winter (DJF in the Northern Hemisphere and JJA in the Southern Hemisphere), the situation is the opposite. Since the SMA and BMA difference results have similar seasonal geographical distributions, this study only analyses the results of the BMA method (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Seasonal geographical distribution of the different values between the BMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000 to 2005; (a–d) and (e–h) are in local spring, summer, fall, and winter in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres, respectively (in units of W m^{-2}).

Figure 9. Seasonal geographical distribution of the different values between the SMA results and the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000 to 2005. (a–d) and (e–h) are in local spring, summer, fall, and winter in the South and Northern Hemispheres, respectively (in units of $W m^{-2}$).

During spring in the Northern Hemisphere, the BMA method tends to overestimate the *SSR* over the Norwegian Sea, the Danish Strait, and the Davis Strait, and underestimate the *SSR* over the land and the central Arctic Ocean compared with the CERES EBAF. In the Southern Hemisphere, the *SSR* is overestimated over the Weddell Sea and the Ross Sea, and over the coastal areas of the Antarctic continent. During summer, the underestimation of the *SSR* is the most prominent over the central Arctic region, with local positive biases presented around the ocean near Greenland and the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and the ocean and land near the Bering Strait. The ocean near Greenland and the land of Eurasia and North America shows a widespread overestimation.

Figure 8c,g shows the differences in the *SSR* between the BMA results and the CERES EBAF during fall. In the Northern Hemisphere, the central Arctic Ocean, Europe, Iceland, Alaska, and coast of Greenland are the areas with the most obvious underestimations. In the Southern Hemisphere, the south Atlantic and the Bellingshausen Sea show a large underestimation, while the rest of the ocean typically shows a large overestimation. The coast of Antarctica shows a large underestimation, while the central and eastern areas of Antarctica show a large overestimation. As shown in Figure 8d, the underestimation of the *SSR* during winter occurs primarily over the coasts. The BMA results over coasts are approximately $5 W m^{-2}$ and $20 W m^{-2}$ lower than the CERES EBAF retrievals in the Northern Hemisphere and the Southern Hemisphere, respectively. The overestimation of the *SSR* over ocean is approximately $5 W m^{-2}$ and $20 W m^{-2}$ larger than the CERES EBAF retrievals in the Northern Hemisphere and the Southern Hemisphere, respectively.

To further investigate the precision differences of the *SSR* estimates in the bright (spring and summer) and dark (fall and winter) seasons, we also compared the seasonal geographical distribution of the normalized differences between the MME results and the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000 to 2005. The normalized values were obtained by the *SSR* estimates divided by the mean *SSR* for the respective season. It was found that the normalized differences between the MME results and CERES EBAF retrievals were smaller than those for the unnormalized differences in both the Northern and the Southern Hemispheres in each season, but such differences between the bright and dark seasons were still obvious. This large seasonal discrepancy indicated that the GCM *SSR* simulations exhibited different precision in the bright and dark seasons.

4.3. Comparing and Evaluating the GCM Simulations and the MME Results with the CERES EBAF Retrievals

It has been reported that some of the CMIP5 GCMs have large biases when simulating cloud water and ice paths compared to satellite retrievals [36], and clouds can have a significant influence on the *SSR* simulation. To understand the differences between the GCMs and the CERES EBAF in

estimating the SSR over high-latitude areas, this study calculated the bias, RMSE, R, and NSE values of each GCM simulations compared with the CERES EBAF retrievals, as shown in Figures 10 and 11. In addition, this study also used Taylor diagrams (Figures 12 and 13) to show the gaps among the SSR outputs from the individual GCMs, the SMA method and the BMA method and the CERES EBAF.

Figure 10. Seasonal statistical results of the SSR simulations from 48 GCMs in CMIP5 with the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000 to 2005 in the Northern Hemisphere. (a) RMSE, (b) Bias, (c) R, (d) NSE (in units of $W m^{-2}$).

Figure 11. Seasonal statistical results of the SSR simulations from 48 GCMs in CMIP5 with the CERES EBAF retrievals from 2000 to 2005 in the Southern Hemisphere. (a) RMSE, (b) Bias, (c) R, (d) NSE (in units of $W m^{-2}$).

Figure 12. Taylor diagram of the estimations from the SMA method, the BMA method, the CERES EBAF, and the 48 GCMs over high-latitude areas from 2000 to 2005 in the Northern Hemisphere. The SMA method, the BMA method, the CERES EBAF, and the 48 GCMs are represented by purple, green, blue, and black dots, respectively. (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c) fall, (d) winter.

Figure 13. Taylor diagram of the estimations from the SMA method, the BMA method, the CERES EBAF, and the 48 GCMs over high-latitude areas from 2000 to 2005 in the Southern Hemisphere. The SMA method, the BMA method, the CERES EBAF, and the 48 GCMs are represented by purple, green, blue, and black dots, respectively. (a) Spring, (b) summer, (c) fall, (d) winter.

In the Northern Hemisphere, as shown in Figure 10a, most of the GCM *SSR* simulations exhibit relatively greater RMSE values in boreal summer than those in other seasons. A total of 39 out of 48 GCM *SSR* simulations show an underestimation tendency compared with ground measurements in summer (JJA). The possible reason may be that the GCMs have difficulties in capturing the insulating effect of clouds, since cloud properties represented by GCM *SSR* estimation models are one of the most important factors in regulating the estimated *SSR*. The *SSR* simulations from BMA method have the smallest RMSE values compared to any *SSR* estimates from individual GCM and the SMA method. Figure 10b shows that the absolute bias values of GCM *SSR* simulations are relatively smaller in fall (SON) and winter (DJF), but greater in summer (JJA). Figure 10c illustrates the R values of the *SSR* estimates. It is obvious that the R values for each GCM and the MME method are relatively small in summer (JJA). As shown in Figure 10d, all the NSE values of *SSR* estimates are greater than zero, except the BNU-ESM (−0.17) and CMCC-CESM (−0.87). The NSE values of the *SSR* estimations from individual GCMs, the SMA method, and the BMA method in spring (MAM), fall (SON), and winter (DJF) are greater than those in summer (JJA). Among the individual GCM *SSR* simulations, the NSE values

of GFDL-CM3 (0.94), HadGEM2-CC (0.77), Inmcm4(0.95), and GISS-E2-R-CC (0.97) *SSR* simulations are the greatest ones in local spring, summer, fall, and winter, respectively.

In the Southern Hemisphere, as shown in Figure 11a, the *SSR* evaluation results are similar to those in the Northern Hemisphere in the local spring, fall, and winter seasons. The biases shown in Figure 11b indicate that the underestimation tendency in the Northern Hemisphere does not exist in Southern Hemisphere. As shown in Figure 11c, the *R* values of the *SSR* estimates are greater than those in Northern Hemisphere, especially in summer. In both Northern and Southern Hemispheres, the BMA method *SSR* simulations have greater NSE values than any individual GCM and the SMA method *SSR* simulations.

In both the Hemispheres, the Taylor diagrams (Figures 12 and 13) show that the MME methods generally have better performance in simulating the *SSR* than the individual GCMs, except in local winter. According to these figures, it is obvious that the distribution of the spots is relatively scattered in local summer. It indicates that the differences in uncertainty of GCM *SSR* simulations are greater in local summer than in other seasons for both Northern and Southern Hemispheres. Additionally, the performance of the CERES EBAF *SSR* retrievals is not always the best among the *SSR* estimations from individual GCMs, SMA method, and BMA method in four seasons (Figures 12 and 13). Therefore, we conclude that the BMA method exhibited relatively better performance in simulating *SSR* compared to individual GCMs and the SMA method.

5. Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the *SSR* simulations and intercompared the performance of both the SMA and BMA methods for estimating the *SSR* in high-latitude areas using quality-controlled surface observations at 44 sites from three *SSR* observation networks (BSRN, GC-NET, and GEBA) and the CERES EBAF *SSR* retrievals from 2000 to 2005.

The evaluation results indicated that the precision of each GCM *SSR* simulations were quite different and GCMs with higher spatial resolutions did not guarantee better performance in simulating *SSR*. Relative to ground observations, the bias, RMSE, and *R* values of the *SSR* simulations ranged from -30 W m^{-2} to 15 W m^{-2} , 20 W m^{-2} to 50 W m^{-2} and 0.94 to 0.99, respectively. Previous studies showed that the GCM *SSR* simulations exhibit a tendency toward excessive *SSR* at the Earth's surface [11]. However, the validation results indicated that the GCM *SSR* simulations did not show an obvious tendency to overestimate the *SSR* over high-latitude areas in this study. Only slightly more than half of the GCMs (26 out of the 48 GCMs) overestimated the *SSR* over high-latitude areas when compared with the ground observations, although some discrepancies between the current GCM *SSR* simulations and ground measurements still existed over high-latitude areas. Cloud and aerosol properties represented by the GCMs are two important factors in regulating the estimated *SSR* [9]. The GCMs have been reported to overestimate aerosol optical thickness [48] and total cloud cover over high-latitude areas [9,36,47]. Thus, the excessive total cloud cover and aerosol optical thickness possibly contribute to the offset of the overestimation of the *SSR* in many of the GCMs. More data including the parameters related to cloud and aerosol are needed to conduct further investigation over high-latitude areas.

Besides cloud and aerosols, measurement errors, such as instrument replacement and drift and spatial representativeness of ground measurements were also potential error sources of *SSR* evaluations. For example, the monthly representation errors at the surface sites with respect to their 1° surroundings are on average 3.7% (4 W m^{-2}) [49]. The GCMs have different spatial resolution that varies from $0.56^\circ \times 0.56^\circ$ to $3.75^\circ \times 3.75^\circ$ which might cause certain biases for the *SSR* evaluation.

The function of the BMA method for the improvements of the *SSR* estimations was estimated based on the change in statistical calculations and Taylor diagrams. The performance of the BMA method was superior to that of any single GCM in simulating the *SSR* over high-latitude areas, especially during summer. Our results also showed that the use of different weights obtained by the BMA method for each GCM based on its performance can be a good alternative to the SMA method.

The BMA simulations were also compared with the CERES EBAF retrievals, and there were noteworthy geographical patterns in the differences between them over high-latitude areas.

Generally, the MME methods where the GCM weights are determined by the GCMs prior performance performs better than the SMA method, e.g., [24,50–54]. Some studies have also obtained similar estimates generated by different MME methods (e.g., [24,55]), which partially reflects the alleged “equifinality” in which different combinations of GCM weights produce identical fit to the ground measurements. The performance of BMA method may be influenced by the training sample sizes. Although the advantage of BMA method was not apparent in this study, the BMA method provides a new option to generate more accurate SSR simulations through the entire ensemble of the model first considered.

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